

**Spectral Characteristics of Nasalization and a Measure of the
Degree of Nasality of Oral Vowels**

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The study attempts to identify a reselected set of measures that can reflect the difference in the degree of nasality between the oral vowel and the nasalized vowel within a pair and the measures that can be used to compare the degree of nasality of a pair of oral vowels with similar vowel height in the acoustic vowel space, based on the spectral characteristics of nasal consonants and vowel nasalization, and, as a supplementary method, to examine whether the degree of nasality of the front vowel is higher than that of the back vowel with similar vowel height in the acoustic vowel space of oral vowels without using nasometry, in order to explain the difference in the front–back asymmetry between the vowel space of nasal vowels and that of oral vowels. The recordings include nasal consonants, oral vowels and nasalized vowels produced normally (without a nose clip), and oral vowels and nasalized vowels produced with a nose clip or other methods affecting the part of the signal corresponding to the nasal branch. The comparison is made within the same speaker. These measures are inspired by the acoustic correlates A1-P0 and A1-P1 described in Chen (1996).

Based on the formant data of a speaker's nasal consonants, the center frequencies and the ranges of the peaks in the response of the speaker's nasal cavity could be estimated. During the production of most nasal consonants, the vocal tract has a side branch formed by the oral residual cavity. The length of this branch affects the phase difference of its part of the signal and the frequency of the peak of its response. The center frequency of its first peak and the frequency at which the phase difference of the component is π are the same, which affects the frequency of an antiformant. For the velar nasal consonant, the antiformants are higher than the first four formants. For nasal consonants whose place of articulation is anterior to the velum and at or posterior to the hard palate, there is at most one antiformant within the frequency range from about 1850 Hz to the set formant ceiling. The data of the formants near the antiformant do not match the true response of the nasal cavity, therefore, the formants outside the antiformant range are selected.

From ①the frequency band of nasal consonant formants obtained above and ②the frequency band with a bandwidth of 40 Hz whose center frequency is the frequency with the largest

amplitude at the peak associated with the strongest harmonic within the range of the first formant of each sample of vowel individually, the sound pressure levels ① L_{N_n} (dB) and ② L_{F_1} (dB) could be respectively obtained, for each sample in a pair of oral and nasalized vowels. By selecting the L_{N_n} (dB) corresponding to the band that does not overlap with the vowel formants, the $L_{N_n} - L_{F_1}$ (dB) could reflect the difference in nasality between the oral vowel and the nasalized vowel within a pair.

Next, the study aims to identify those measures that can be used to compare the degree of nasality of mid, low-mid or low vowels in oral vowels with similar vowel height in the acoustic vowel space. From each sample in a pair of front and back oral vowels of the same speaker, the frequency with the largest amplitude at the peak associated with the harmonic that is the closest to the first formant of the nasal consonant of the same speaker are taken. For the frequency band whose band floor f_1 (Hz) is the lowest of these frequencies minus 20 Hz and whose band ceiling f_2 (Hz) is the highest of these frequencies plus 20 Hz, the time-averaged sound pressure squared of this band could be obtained and denoted as p^2_N (Pa²) or $p^2_{Nnoseclip}$ (Pa²); the quantity without the subscript "noseclip" refers to the value of the oral vowel produced normally, and the quantity with the subscript "noseclip" refers to the value of the oral vowel produced with a nose clip or other methods affecting the part of the signal corresponding to the nasal branch, and the same applies below. The samples with f_2 below 300 Hz are selected.

$$p^2_N = \frac{1}{t} \sum_{k=k_1}^{k_2} p_f^2(k), \quad p^2_{Nnoseclip} = \frac{1}{t'} \sum_{k=k_{1noseclip}}^{k_{2noseclip}} p_{f,noseclip}^2(k). \quad p_f^2(i) \text{ (Pa}^2 \cdot \text{s) and } p_{f,noseclip}^2(i) \text{ (Pa}^2 \cdot \text{s) are respectively the sums of the sound pressure squared over the}$$

discrete time samples of the signal component corresponding to the i -th frequency bin in the discrete frequency domain; $p_f^2(i) = \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} x_i^2(n) \Delta t$, $i \in [k_1, k_2]$; $p_{f,noseclip}^2(i) =$

$$\sum_{n=0}^{N_{noseclip}-1} x_{i,noseclip}^2(n) \Delta t, \quad i \in [k_{1noseclip}, k_{2noseclip}]. \quad x_i^2(n) \text{ (Pa}^2) \text{ and } x_{i,noseclip}^2(n)$$

(Pa^2) are respectively the components corresponding to the i -th frequency bin of the sound pressure squared $x^2(n)$ (Pa^2) and $x^2_{noseclip}(n)$ (Pa^2) in the discrete time domain.

Let $p^2_a(f) = \frac{1}{f_2-f_1} p^2_N$, $f \in [f_1, f_2]$, and $p^2_{anoseclip}(f) = \frac{1}{f_2-f_1} p^2_{Nnoseclip}$, $f \in [f_1, f_2]$.

$f_0 \in [f_1, f_2]$. $p^2_a(f_0) = \frac{1}{t} \int_0^t x_{af_0}^2(t) dt = \frac{1}{t} \int_0^t \frac{1}{f_2-f_1} x_{[f_1, f_2]}^2(t) dt = \frac{1}{t} \frac{1}{f_2-f_1} \int_{f_1}^{f_2} p_f^2(f) df$, and

$p^2_{anoseclip}(f_0) = \frac{1}{t_{noseclip}} \int_0^{t_{noseclip}} x_{af_0noseclip}^2(t) dt =$

$\frac{1}{t_{noseclip}} \int_0^{t_{noseclip}} \frac{1}{f_2-f_1} x_{[f_1, f_2]noseclip}^2(t) dt = \frac{1}{t_{noseclip}} \frac{1}{f_2-f_1} \int_{f_1}^{f_2} p_f^2_{noseclip}(f) df$. $x_{af_0}^2(t)$

and $x_{af_0noseclip}^2(t)$ are respectively the components corresponding to the frequency f_0 , in

the time domain. $x_{af_0}^2(t) = (x_o(t) + x_n(t))^2$, and $x_{af_0noseclip}^2(t) = (x_{onoseclip}(t) + x_{nnoseclip}(t))^2$. The symbols $x_o(t)$ and $x_{onoseclip}(t)$ represent respectively the parts of the

signal corresponding to the oral branch (excluding the nasal part of the signal that is reflected within the nasal cavity, passes through the velopharyngeal port, and is subsequently radiated to the outside through the oral cavity vocal tract); $x_o(t) = A_o \cos(\omega t)$, and $x_{onoseclip}(t) =$

$A_{onoseclip} \cos(\omega t)$. The symbols $x_n(t)$ and $x_{nnoseclip}(t)$ represent respectively the parts of the signal corresponding to the nasal branch (including the part of the signal that is reflected within the nasal cavity, not only the part radiated to the outside through the nostrils); $x_n(t) =$

$A_n \cos(\omega t + \varphi)$; $x_{nnoseclip}(t) = A_{nnoseclip} \cos(\omega t + \varphi_{noseclip})$, $A_{nnoseclip} =$

$\left(A_{nnoseclip_1}^2 + A_{nnoseclip_2}^2 + 2A_{nnoseclip_1} A_{nnoseclip_2} \cos(\varphi_{noseclip_1} - \varphi_{noseclip_2}) \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}$,
 $\cos(\varphi_{noseclip}) = \pm \frac{1}{\left(1 + \left(\frac{A_{nnoseclip_1} \sin(\varphi_{noseclip_1}) + A_{nnoseclip_2} \sin(\varphi_{noseclip_2})}{A_{nnoseclip_1} \cos(\varphi_{noseclip_1}) + A_{nnoseclip_2} \cos(\varphi_{noseclip_2})} \right)^2 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}}$. The symbols A_o

and $A_{onoseclip}$ represent respectively the amplitude values of the parts of the signal

corresponding to the oral branch. The symbol A_n represents the amplitude value of the part of the signal corresponding to the nasal branch; for the nasal cavity component, during normal production, the part radiated to the outside through the nostrils is the majority. The symbol

$A_{nnoseclip_1}$ represents the amplitude value of the nasal part of the signal that transmits to the

outside through human tissue when the nose clip is used; the symbol $A_{n_{noseclip_2}}$ represents the amplitude value of the nasal part of the signal that, when the nose clip is used, is reflected, passes through the velopharyngeal port, and is subsequently radiated to the outside through the oral cavity vocal tract; the symbols φ , $\varphi_{noseclip_1}$ and $\varphi_{noseclip_2}$ represent respectively the phase differences of those parts relative to the part of the signal corresponding to the oral branch; the length of the nasal cavity is less than $\frac{1}{2} \frac{\pi}{600\pi}$ m, and $\varphi_{noseclip_1} < \varphi_{noseclip_2}$; therefore, $\cos(\varphi_{noseclip_1}) > \cos(\varphi_{noseclip_2}) > 0$, and $\sin(\varphi_{noseclip_2}) > \sin(\varphi_{noseclip_1}) \geq 0$; therefore, $\varphi_{noseclip} \in (\varphi_{noseclip_1}, \varphi_{noseclip_2})$; therefore, $\cos(\varphi_{noseclip}) > 0$; therefore, $\cos(\varphi_{noseclip}) = \frac{1}{\left(1 + \left(\frac{A_{noseclip_1} \sin(\varphi_{noseclip_1}) + A_{noseclip_2} \sin(\varphi_{noseclip_2})}{A_{noseclip_1} \cos(\varphi_{noseclip_1}) + A_{noseclip_2} \cos(\varphi_{noseclip_2})}\right)^2\right)^{\frac{1}{2}}}$; if the impedance of the velopharyngeal port becomes lower, the increase in $A_{n_{noseclip_2}}$ is greater than the increase in $A_{n_{noseclip_1}}$. Therefore, if the degree of nasality of the oral vowel produced normally becomes higher, $\cos(\varphi_{noseclip})$ becomes smaller; if all other conditions are the same, a smaller $\cos(\varphi_{noseclip})$ corresponds to a higher degree of nasality.

$r_o = \frac{A_o}{A_{o_{noseclip}}}$. The symbol r_o represents the ratio of the amplitude value of the part of the signal corresponding to the oral branch between the two productions, influenced by uncertainty from the source between the two productions and the increase in nasal impedance. If the degree of nasality of the oral vowel produced normally becomes higher, r_o becomes smaller; if all other conditions are the same, a smaller r_o corresponds to a higher degree of nasality.

The bands for p^2_N and $p^2_{N_{noseclip}}$ are below the second formant and the third formant of vowels, and the back vowel has lower second and third formant frequencies than the front vowel. Therefore, the response of the oral filter of the back vowel in this band is stronger than that of the front vowel, which increases A_o .

$$r_n = \frac{A_n}{A_{nnoseclip}} = \frac{1}{\left(\frac{A_{noseclip_1}^2}{A_n^2} + \frac{A_{noseclip_2}^2}{A_n^2} + 2\frac{A_{noseclip_1}A_{noseclip_2}}{A_n^2}\cos(\varphi_{noseclip_1} - \varphi_{noseclip_2})\right)^{\frac{1}{2}}}. \text{ The}$$

symbol r_n represents the ratio of the amplitude value of the part of the signal corresponding to the nasal branch between the two productions, which is influenced by the decrease of this amplitude value due to production with a nose clip, the phase difference due to the path difference, and the change in amplitude due to the uncertainty from the source between the two productions. If the degree of nasality of the oral vowel produced normally becomes higher, r_n becomes larger; if all other conditions are the same, a larger r_n corresponds to a higher degree of nasality.

A frequency band in which the proportion of the part of the signal corresponding to the nasal branch is comparatively small should be selected, and it needs to satisfy the condition that the effect of the response of the oral filter of front vowels in this band is stronger than that of back vowels. Therefore, the frequency band from the frequency at or above an approximate reference frequency of 6000 Hz to the Nyquist frequency could be taken, and the time-averaged sound pressure squared of this band could be denoted as p^2_1 (Pa^2) and $p^2_{1noseclip}$ (Pa^2). $r_1 = \frac{p^2_1}{p^2_{1noseclip}}$. As the proportion of the part of the signal corresponding to the nasal branch in this band is close to its minimum across the entire frequency range, choosing this band reduces the influence of the nasal branch, and $r_1 \approx r_o^2$. If the degree of nasality of the oral vowel produced normally becomes higher, r_1 becomes smaller; if all other conditions are the same, a smaller r_1 corresponds to a higher degree of nasality.

For the oral vowels produced normally and the oral vowels produced with a nose clip, the change in the response of the nasal filter is approximately the same between the front vowel and the back vowel, and there is also no obvious tendency for the first formant of the vowel to shift in the previously obtained data.

The samples are selected based on several criteria: samples whose speaker's repeated vowel productions have smaller differences in formant frequencies; samples whose harmonic closest to the first formant of the nasal consonant is different from the strongest harmonic within the first formant range of the vowel; samples whose speaker's nasal consonant formant frequencies are comparatively lower; samples whose difference between the maximum and minimum fundamental frequencies does not exceed 15 Hz, with a preference for smaller fundamental frequency differences.

The duration of the audio cut from the original audio is close to an integer multiple of the fundamental period and as long as possible, and the frequencies that are the integer multiples of the fundamental frequency are the frequencies at the peak associated with harmonics, that is, the frequencies whose amplitudes are the largest ones within the band. After time averaging, $\cos^2(\omega t)$ and $\cos^2(\omega t + \varphi)$ are approximately equal to 1/2, and $\cos(2\omega t + \varphi)$ is approximately equal to 0.

Let $\Delta(p^2_N/p^2_1) = p^2_N/p^2_1 - p^2_{Nnoseclip}/p^2_{1noseclip}$. If $\Delta(p^2_N/p^2_1)_{\text{front vowel}} >$

$\Delta(p^2_N/p^2_1)_{\text{back vowel}}$, then $(\frac{1}{f_2-f_1}p^2_N - \frac{1}{f_2-f_1}p^2_{Nnoseclip})_{\text{front vowel}} > (\frac{1}{f_2-f_1}p^2_N -$

$\frac{1}{f_2-f_1}p^2_{Nnoseclip})_{\text{back vowel}}$, then $(\frac{p^2_a(f_0)}{p^2_1} - \frac{p^2_{anoseclip}(f_0)}{p^2_{1noseclip}})_{\text{front vowel}} > (\frac{p^2_a(f_0)}{p^2_1} -$

$\frac{p^2_{anoseclip}(f_0)}{p^2_{1noseclip}})_{\text{back vowel}}$.

$$\frac{p^2_a(f_0)}{p^2_1} - \frac{p^2_{anoseclip}(f_0)}{p^2_{1noseclip}}$$

$$\frac{\frac{1}{t} \int_0^t x_{af_0}^2(t) dt}{p^2_1} - \frac{\frac{1}{t_{noseclip}} \int_0^{t_{noseclip}} x_{af_0}^2(t) dt}{p^2_{1noseclip}}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{\frac{1}{t} \int_0^t (x_o(t) + x_n(t))^2 dt}{p^2_1} - \frac{\frac{1}{t_{noseclip}} \int_0^{t_{noseclip}} (x_{onoseclip}(t) + x_{nnoseclip}(t))^2 dt}{p^2_{1noseclip}} \\
& \frac{\frac{1}{t} \int_0^t (A_o \cos(\omega t) + A_n \cos(\omega t + \varphi))^2 dt}{p^2_1} - \frac{\frac{1}{t_{noseclip}} \int_0^{t_{noseclip}} (A_{onoseclip} \cos(\omega t) + A_{nnoseclip} \cos(\omega t + \varphi_{noseclip}))^2 dt}{p^2_{1noseclip}} \\
& \frac{\frac{1}{t} \int_0^t (A_o^2 \cos^2(\omega t) + A_n^2 \cos^2(\omega t + \varphi) + 2A_o A_n (\cos(2\omega t + \varphi) + \cos(\varphi))) dt}{p^2_1} - \\
& \frac{\frac{1}{t_{noseclip}} \int_0^{t_{noseclip}} (A_{onoseclip}^2 \cos^2(\omega t) + A_{nnoseclip}^2 \cos^2(\omega t + \varphi) + 2A_{onoseclip} A_{nnoseclip} (\cos(2\omega t + \varphi_{noseclip}) + \cos(\varphi_{noseclip}))) dt}{p^2_{1'}} \\
& \approx \frac{\frac{1}{2} (A_n^2 - r_1 A_{nnoseclip}^2) + 2(A_o A_n \cos(\varphi) - r_1^{\frac{1}{2}} A_o A_{nnoseclip} \cos(\varphi_{noseclip}))}{p^2_1} \\
& \frac{\frac{1}{2} A_n^2 \left(1 - \frac{r_1}{r_n^2}\right) + 2A_o A_n \left(\cos(\varphi) - \frac{r_1^{\frac{1}{2}}}{r_n} \cos(\varphi_{noseclip})\right)}{p^2_1}
\end{aligned}$$

As $0 < \cos(\varphi_{noseclip}) \leq 1$, $\cos(\varphi) - \frac{r_1^{\frac{1}{2}}}{r_n} * \cos(\varphi_{noseclip}) \geq 0$ if $\frac{r_1^{\frac{1}{2}}}{r_n} \leq \cos(\varphi)$. $\frac{r_1^{\frac{1}{2}}}{r_n} \leq r_{11}^{\frac{1}{2}}$; the symbol r_{11} represents the $\frac{p^2_1}{p^2_{1noseclip}}$ of the vowel sample whose first half is produced normally and whose second half is produced while pinching the nose. From the previously obtained data, $r_{11}^{\frac{1}{2}} \leq \cos\left(\frac{2\pi * 300 * 0.08}{350}\right)$; $\cos\varphi = \cos\left(\frac{2\pi * f * \Delta L}{c}\right)$, $f \leq 300\text{Hz}$, $c \approx 350\text{ m/s}$, $\varphi \geq 0$, and the path difference ΔL between the oral cavity and nasal cavity vocal tracts is less than 0.08 m, therefore, $\cos\varphi \geq \cos\left(\frac{2\pi * 300 * 0.08}{350}\right)$. Therefore, $\cos(\varphi) - \frac{r_1^{\frac{1}{2}}}{r_n} * \cos(\varphi_{noseclip}) > 0$. In addition, $\frac{r_1}{r_n^2} < 1$.

Therefore, if $\Delta(p^2_N/p^2_1)_{\text{front vowel}} > \Delta(p^2_N/p^2_1)_{\text{back vowel}}$, then there must be

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left(\frac{A_n^2}{p^2_1}\right)_{\text{front vowel}} > \left(\frac{A_n^2}{p^2_1}\right)_{\text{back vowel}} \text{ or } \left(1 - \frac{r_1}{r_n^2}\right)_{\text{front vowel}} > \left(1 - \frac{r_1}{r_n^2}\right)_{\text{back vowel}} \text{ or} \\
& \left(\frac{A_o * A_n}{p^2_1}\right)_{\text{front vowel}} > \left(\frac{A_o * A_n}{p^2_1}\right)_{\text{back vowel}} \text{ or } \left(\cos(\varphi) - \frac{r_1^{\frac{1}{2}}}{r_n} * \cos(\varphi_{noseclip})\right)_{\text{front vowel}} > \\
& \left(\cos(\varphi) - \frac{r_1^{\frac{1}{2}}}{r_n} * \cos(\varphi_{noseclip})\right)_{\text{back vowel}}.
\end{aligned}$$

If ①the response of the oral filter of the front vowel in the frequency band of p^2_1 is stronger than that of the back vowel (the second and third formant frequencies of the front vowel are higher), and if ②the response of the oral filter of the back vowel in the band of p^2_N is stronger than that of the front vowel (the back vowel has lower second and third formant frequencies, which have greater effect on the band of p^2_N), then the above inequalities can show that the degree of nasality of the front vowel is higher than that of the back vowel with similar vowel height in the acoustic vowel space of oral vowels. Therefore, the frequency band from the frequency at or above an approximate reference frequency of 6000 Hz to the Nyquist frequency could be used for p^2_1 (the band near the first formant does not satisfy the first condition①).

Therefore, for mid, low-mid or low vowels with similar first formant frequencies in oral vowels, if the $\Delta(p^2_N/p^2_1)$ of the front vowel is larger than that of the back vowel, this indicates that, for mid, low-mid or low vowels with similar vowel height in the acoustic vowel space of oral vowels, the degree of nasality of the front vowel is higher than that of the back vowel.

Due to the limitations of the recording environment, the time-averaged sound pressure squared of the band is influenced by the high-frequency noise. Therefore, the sum of the time-averaged sound pressure squared of the band from 6000 Hz to the Nyquist frequency and the time-averaged sound pressure squared of the band whose band floor is the lowest of the set of frequencies with the largest amplitude at the peak associated with the strongest harmonic within the range of the first formant of each sample from the set of vowels used for comparison minus 20 Hz and whose band ceiling is the highest frequency of this set of frequencies plus 20 Hz is used as p^2_1 and $p^2_{1noseclip}$. The band near the first formant still contains the part of the signal corresponding to the nasal branch and does not satisfy the condition that the response of the oral filter of the front vowel in this band is stronger than

that of the back vowel. It is used only because of the recording environment. If a better recording environment is available to avoid high-frequency noise, then the frequency band from the frequency at or above an approximate reference frequency of 6000 Hz to the Nyquist frequency could be chosen. The recordings were collected using a customized microphone with a Primo EM272z1 microphone capsule; the 0° and 90° responses are recalibrated using a calibrated B&K 4958-A system (5 Hz - 40 kHz (1/12 oct) < ±0.5 dB) (sound pressure level ±0.3 dB); the system frequency response is calibrated at 10 Hz - 48 kHz, and the uncertainty of frequency response is less than ±1 dB (15 Hz - 30 kHz); the ADC: 96 kHz / 24 bit. For the comparison between the oral vowel and the nasalized vowel, the recordings include Hokkien, Ningbo dialect, French, Japanese and Mandarin; for the comparison between the front vowel and the back vowel in oral vowels, the recordings include Ningbo dialect, French, and Japanese. From the comparison of the values between the nasalized vowel and the oral vowel within a pair, the $\Delta(p^2_N/p^2_1)$ is empirically tested. From these data,

$\Delta(p^2_N/p^2_1)_{\text{nasalized vowel}} > \Delta(p^2_N/p^2_1)_{\text{oral vowel}}$. From these data, $(L_{N_n} -$

$L_{F_1})_{\text{nasalized vowel}} \text{ (dB)} > (L_{N_n} - L_{F_1})_{\text{oral vowel}} \text{ (dB)}$; for mid or low-mid vowels in oral

vowels with similar first formant frequencies, $\Delta(p^2_N/p^2_1)_{\text{front vowel}} >$

$\Delta(p^2_N/p^2_1)_{\text{back vowel}}$. The results could be more reliable if ultrasound or other methods are used to observe the tongue position and if the recording conditions are improved.

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